

Addressing Barriers and Opportunities Engendered by Big Data in Transport: The LeMO Project

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The transport sector has constantly collected and analysed large amounts of data, such as data from timetables, traffic news and air schedules. However, recent developments in the quantity, complexity and availability of such big data collected from and about transport systems, together with advances in information and communication technology, are presenting new opportunities to create more efficient and smarter transport and traffic systems for people and freight [1]. Also, 'opening up' data in transport by making it more widely available, and linking it with data from other sectors, is the part of the European strategy to improve transparency and encourage economic growth.

In transport, the *volume* of data has increased because of growth in the amount of traffic (all modes) and detectors. Also, travellers, goods and vehicles generate more data from mobile devices and tracking transponders (including trains, ships and aircraft). Infrastructure, environmental and meteorological monitoring also produces data that is related to transport operations and users. The *velocity* of data has increased in transport due to improved communications technology and media and increased processing power and speed for monitoring and processing. Some applications have experienced a step change in data velocity as technology has changed. For example, ticketing and tolling transactions that use smart cards or tags are now immediately reported, whereas paper-based ticketing depends on human processing to acquire data from the transactions. The *variety* of transport-related data has increased significantly. Modern trains report internal system telemetry in real time from anywhere in the world and it is possible to acquire information about all crew members and passengers. The *Veracity* refers to the quality, provenance and trust of the data. For deriving knowledge out of volumes of data, the accuracy of the data sources needs to be evaluated as well. Lastly, the *value* is potential gain for an organisation when exploiting the data [2, 3].

The use of big and open data in the transport sector is relevant for governments (traffic control, planning and modelling, route planning, congestion management, etc.), for the private sector (travel industry, route planning and logistics, competitive advantages, etc.) and for individuals (route and travel planning). Big data in transport will lead to improved multi-source traffic and travel data availability and processing, and to tools to enhance multi-source traffic and travel data fusion for, for instance, improved traffic and mobility management.

Big data has opened a wide spectrum of opportunities in the field of transport research. Several challenges will constitute opportunities for researchers (as well as the industry) in the foreseeable future. Observing the recent growing interest in the application of big data within urban transportation, as well as the widened scope of its applications, it is evident that most of the challenges have yet to be addressed.

A new European-funded project, *Leveraging Big Data to Manage Transport Operations (LeMO¹)* project will address these issues by investigating the implications of the utilisation of such big data to enhance the sustainability and competitiveness of European transport sector. The project will study and analyse big data in the European transport domain in particular with respect to five transport dimensions: mode, sector, technology, policy and evaluation.

¹ <https://lemo-h2020.eu/>

The collection, use, sharing and linking of transport big data implicates a number of economic, environmental, legal, social, ethical and political issues, including those which may result in positive and negative societal impact. This presentation at the MFTS2018 focuses on the objectives of the LeMO project and presents a preliminary investigation of some of the aforementioned issues that may be relevant to the consequences produced by big data. LeMO project uses this information as a springboard to further investigate research opportunities, challenges and limitations in relation to specific case studies and, based on their results, develop recommendations and a roadmap, which policy makers will be able to use to make better-informed decisions.

References

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